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Holotype female with 4 labels: 1) [red] “Holotype”; 2) “Deh Bakri / (Djem al Barrez) /
Iran / G. Remaudiere 21-VI-1955”; 3) “*Blepisanis / remaudierei* / n. sp. / A. Villiers det.
1986”; 4) “*Phytoecia / Blepisanis* / [the word is unreadable]” - collection of Muséum
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**New subspecies of *Cerambyx cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Central Russia**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Cerambycini, *Cerambyx cerdo*, new subspecies, Central Russia, Ukraine.

Abstract: *Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo nikolaevi* **ssp. n.** is described from Samara environs. The new subspecies is widely distributed in steppe zone of Eastern Europe.

Introduction

Cerambyx cerdo Linnaeus, 1758 was described as “Habitat in Italia. M. Kähler. in Germania.” The species is widely distributed along northern Palaearctic Region from Iberic Peninsula to European Russia, North Africa, Near East and Caucasus (Danilevsky, 2020). The species is characterized by great geographical and individual variability. Many subspecies were described and traditionally accepted (up to 8), though the number of infraspecific taxa varied from author to author. Certain authors (Sama, 2003) finally were not able to accept any subspecies, because the most peculiar one - *C. c. mirbecki* Lucas, 1842 from North Africa includes specimens indistinguishable from *C. c. cerdo* from Western Europe. But statistically many geographical forms can be easily recognized. New subspecies continue to be described up to now as new populations are studied. So, recently *C. c. masaryki* Vartanis, 2018 from Bulgaria and *C. c. cyprius* Vartanis, 2023 from Cyprus were described.

Meanwhile no specimens of *C. cerdo* were known from central part of European Russia to Plavilstshikov (1940, 1965 - West of Ukraine, Crimea, Caucasus), neither to (Aurivillius, 1912). But K.V. Arnoldi (1953: 179) widened its area eastwards to about Volga (K.V. Arnoldi, 1953: 179). The species was known to him

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(K.V. Arnoldi, 1953: 185) from Tellerman Forest in Voronezh Region and was also recorded for Voronezh Region by Polozhentsev, Alekseev (1959), Negrobov et al. (2005).

C. cerdo was recorded for Ulyanovsk Region by Isaev et al. (2004), Isaev (2004 - Bakhteevka), for Samara Region by Dyuzhaeva & Lyubvina (2000), for Orenburg Region by Simonenkova & Yakimov (2007), for Penza region by Polumordvinov & Monakhov (2007, 2019), for Chuvashia (Cheboksary) by Fadeev, Moskovkin (1979) and Sysoletina, Khmel'kov (1984 - near Cheboksary). Two males from Samara Region (one dated 1956, another one from Zhiguli: 12.7.1973 D.Naturo leg.) are preserved in Samara Natural Museum (D. Magdeev, personal message 2018). One male from Samara ("Kuybyshev, Frunze, 24.5.1975") is preserved in author's collection.

It was included in Red Data Book of many Russian regions: Tatarstan (Khalidov, 1995), Lipetsk (Tsurikov, 2006), Kursk (Dyachenko, 2017), Voronezh (Negrobov & Maslova, 2018), Belgorod (Prisnyi, 2019).

The adequate construction of infraspecific taxonomy of *C. cerdo* must be based on the analysis of numerous specimens from studied area. Single similar specimens could be found in very distant geographical regions, in all subspecies. That is why the demonstration of such specimens (Miroshnikov, 2022) cannot be a decisive argument for uniting of different populations into one subspecies.

The species is one of the biggest and most attractive representatives of European beetles. Earlier (Rudnev, 1953) it was regarded as the most dangerous pest of *Quercus*. Now it is included in the red data books of about all European countries including Russia, as well as in the red data books of several European Russian regions. A huge literature is devoted to various aspects of the biology of the species. A relatively vast revue was published by Miroshnikov (2019).

Results

Cerambyx (s. str.) *cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758

Figs 1-6

- Cerambyx cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758: 392 - "Habitat in Italia. M. Kähler. in Germania"; Lucas, 1847: 485 (= *paludivagus* Lucas, 1842), part. - "dans les bois marécageux du lac Tonga (environs du cercle de Lacalle)"; Ganglbauer, 1882: 744 (= *heros* Scopoli, 1763) - "Europa"; Aurivillius, 1912: 52 (= *heros* Scopoli) - "Mittel- und Südeuropa", including var. *acuminatus* Motsch. - "Krim", *manderstjernae* Muls. & God. - "Syrien", var. *mirbeckii* Lucas - "Mittelmeergebiet", var. *pfisteri* Stierl. - "Sicilien"; Plavilstshikov, 1940: 91, 635 (including ssp. *pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864; ssp. *mirbeckii* Lucas, 1842; ssp. *acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853) - West Europe northwards to Sweden, most of Ukraine, Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Asia Minor, Syria, Iran, North Africa; Medvedev, Bozhko & Shapiro, 1951: 310 - Northern Donets near Svyatogorsk, Provallia Steppe, 314 - steppe zone and south forest-steppe; Arnoldi, 1953: 179, 185 - eastwards to about Volga, Tellerman, Zmiev, Svyatogorsk; Skufiy, 1978: 76 - southeast of the black-earth center (Voronezh Region with neighbor parts of Lipetsk and Belgorod regions; Villiers, 1978: 302 - "l'Europe centrale et méridionale, l'Afrique du Nord, le Caucase, l'Asie Mineure jusque dans l'Iran septentrional"; Khalidov, 1995: 140 - Tatarstan; Vives, 2000: 118; Magdeev, 2003: 207 - Samara Region, Zhiguli; Sama, 2003: 52 (= *heros* Scopoli, 1763); 2010: 50 (= *iranicus* Heyrovský, 1951); Isaev, 2004: 65 - Ulyanovsk Region; Isaev et al., 2004: 38 - Ulyanovsk Region; Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004: 53 - Chernigov Region, Central Dnieper region, Donetsk Region; Tsurikov, 2006: 190 - Lipetsk Region; 2009: 211 - Lipetsk Region; Shumik, 2012: 30 - Krasnyi Styag, Pochep District, Bryansk Region; Polumordvinov & Monakhov, 2017: 286-287 - Penza Region, Neverkino district, Staraya Andreevka (Kadada River); 2019: 48 - Penza Region; Dyachenko, 2018: 49 - Kursk Region: whole European Russia; Glushkovo and L'gov districts; Miroshnikov, 2022: 254 - Europe, West Asia, North Africa.
- Cerambyx heros* Scopoli, 1763: 51 - "Circa Labacum".
- Hamaticherus mirbeckii* Lucas, 1842: 184 - "Assez commune dans le cercle de la Calle"; "dans les bois des lacs Houheira et Tonga"; Algérie.
- Cerambyx mirbeckii*, Lucas, 1847: 484, part. - "dans les bois des lacs Tonga et Houheira" (environs du cercle de Lacalle); "dans les bois de chênes-lièges qui se trouvent entre Stora et Philippeville"; Algérie.
- Cerambyx acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853: 79 - "Georgie et des pays limitrophes de la mer Caspienne".
- Cerambyx manderstjernae* Mulsant & Godart, 1855b: 280 [= 1855a: 180] - "la Crimée".
- Hamaticherus pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864: 152 - "Sicilien", "vorzugsweise in der Gegend von Palermo, aber auch in andern Theilen der Insel".

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- Cerambyx cerdo* [locale Rasse] *acuminatus*, Ganglbauer, 1882: 744 (= *manderstjernae* Muls.) - “Krimm, Caucasus, Türkei, Kleinasien, Syrien”.
- Cerambyx cerdo* [locale Rasse] *pfisteri*, Ganglbauer, 1882: 744 - “Sicilien, Griechenland”.
- Cerambyx cerdo* [locale Rasse] *mirbeckii*, Ganglbauer, 1882: 744 - “Südfrankreich, Spanien, Corsica, Algier”.
- Hammaticherus cerdo*, Sakharov, 1903: 65 - Balashov district of Saratov Region.
- Cerambyx cerdo cerdo*, Plavilstshikov, 1940: 91, 635 (= *heros* Scopoli, 1763), part. - West Europe northwards to Sweden, west of Ukraine eastwards to about Kharkov; Villiers, 1978: 304 - “Europe centrale et méridionale”; Sama, 2003: 53, part. (= *acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853 = *pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864 = *mirbeckii* Lucas, 1842); 2011: 549 - Sardinia; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 159 (= *acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853 = *heros* Scopoli, 1763 = *iranicus* Heyrovský, 1951 = *klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 = *manderstjernae* Mulsant & Godart, 1855 = *pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864), part. - Europe eastwards to Ukraine, Caucasus, Near East; Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 134 - Italy; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 201 - “Europa centrale e meridionale, in quella settentrionale fino alla Svezia; Africa sett., Caucaso, Asia Minore, Iran”; Sama et al., 2012: 29 - Turkey; Sláma, 2019: 199, part.; Vartanis, 2023: 762, part. - “Czechia, Hungary, Austria, France, Italy, Croatia, Slovakia, Ukraine, Moldavia, Turkey, Polonia, Macedonia”.
- Cerambyx cerdo mirbecki*, Villiers, 1946: 78-79 - Maroc, Algérie, Tunisie.
- Cerambyx cerdo iranicus* Heyrovský, 1951: 156, 157 - “Soud-ouest de l'Iran, Bushir dans le Golfe perse”; Villiers, 1967b: 353, part. - “Iran: Bushir”; Sláma, 2019: 200, 201, part.; Danilevsky, 2020a: 71, part.
- Cerambyx cerdo morpha laevicollis* Heyrovský, 1955: 156 (unavailable name) - Třeboň environs (Czech Republic), after private letter (2023) by M. Sláma.
- Cerambyx cerdo acuminatus*, Villiers, 1967a: 20 - “Turquie”; 1967b: 353, part. - “Crimée, Asie Mineure, Arménie, Caucase, Nord de l'Iran”; Sláma, 2019: 203, part. - “eastern areas”; Miroshnikov, 2022: 259 (= *manderstjernae* Mulsant & Godart, 1855); Vartanis, 2023: 762, part.
- Cerambyx cerdo mirbeckii*, Compte-Sart & Carreras-Torrent, 2016: 88, part. - “Propio de Argelia, Túnez y Marruecos”; Vives, 2000: 118-119 - “la única presente en la región ibero-baleár”; “en Africa del Norte”, “en toda la Península [Ibérica] e islas Baleares”; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 159 (= *tunisicus* Pic, 1891), part. - Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia; Sláma, 2019: 204, part. - “North Africa”; Danilevsky, 2020a: 71, part.; Vartanis, 2023: 762, part.
- Cerambyx cerdo mirbeckii* var. *tunisicus*, Compte-Sart & Carreras-Torrent, 2016: 88, part. - “Túnez”.
- Cerambyx cerdo cerdo* var. *acuminatus*, Compte-Sart & Carreras-Torrent, 2016: 88, part. - “Dalmacia, Crimea, Cáucaso, Turmenia [sic], Turquía, Siria, Irán etc.”.
- Cerambyx cerdo cerdo* var. *pfisteri*, Compte-Sart & Carreras-Torrent, 2016: 88, part. - “Italia, Grecia y al parecer de Francia y Córcega”.

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- Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo acuminatus*, Cocquempot & al., 2016: 96, part. - Liban; Lazarev, 2019a: 22, 52, part. - “De la Georgie et des pays limitrophes de la mer Caspienne”; 2019b: 1257, part. - lectotype label: “Turkmenia Georgia”; Danilevsky, 2020c: 215, part. (= *klinzigi* Podaný, 1964) - south of European Russia, Ukraine, Transcaucasia, Near East; Miroschnikov, 2021: 459, 463 (= *manderstjerna* Mulsant & Godart, 1855), part.; Gubin & Martynov, 2023: 160 - Donetsk Region, Svyatogorsk environs.
- Cerambyx cerdo masaryki* Vartanis, 2018: 76 - “Bulgaria”; 2023: 760, 762, part. - “Bulgaria”.
- Cerambyx iranicus* [?], Sláma, 2019: 202, part.
- Cerambyx cerdo pfisteri*, Villiers, 1978: 304 - “Sicile et s’étend jusqu’en Grèce”; Sláma, 2019: 204, part. - “Corsica and Sicily”; Danilevsky, 2020a: 71, part.; Vartanis, 2023: 762, part. - “Greece, Italy”.
- Cerambyx cerdo manderstjerna*, Danilevsky, 2020b: 3 - Crimea and Black Sea coast (Sochi environs).
- Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo cerdo*, Danilevsky, 2020c: 215 - Europe.
- Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo manderstjerna*, Danilevsky, 2020c: 215 - south of European Russia, Ukraine.
- Cerambyx cerdo cyprius* Vartanis, 2023: 760 - “Cyprus”.

Description. Body dark brown, sometimes nearly black anteriorly, more or less lightened posteriorly; male antennae much longer than body; female antennae a little shorter or a little longer than body; 2nd antennal joint short, strongly transverse; 3rd and 4th antennal joints never strongly swollen; pronotum usually with numerous irregular plications sometimes more or less arranged transversely; very rare pronotum smooth and mirror-shiny as in *C. cerdo morpha laevicollis* Heyrovský, 1955 (population near Třeboň, Czech Republic); elytra strongly (males) or slightly (females) narrowed backwards, more or less roughly sculptured anteriorly and nearly smooth posteriorly; body length: 23–55 mm.

Distribution. About whole Europe from Iberian Peninsula to about Urals (excluding northern and desert regions without oaks), North Africa, Caucasus with Transcaucasia, Near East eastwards to Iran.

The problem of taxonomic interpretation of Eastern European populations of *C. cerdo* has long been recognized by entomologists (Polumordvinov & Monakhov, 2007). Below poorly known populations from Central Russia are recognized as a new subspecies.

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Cerambyx (s. str.) *cerdo nikolaevi* ssp. n.

Figs 1-2, Map 1

Hammaticherus cerdo, Sakharov, 1903: 65 - Balashov district of Saratov Region.

Cerambyx cerdo, Medvedev, Bozhko & Shapiro, 1951: 310 - Northern Donets near Svyatogorsk, Provallia Steppe, 314 - steppe zone and south forest-steppe; Arnoldi, 1953: 179, 185 - eastwards to about Volga, Tellerman, Zmiev, Svyatogorsk; Polozhentsev & Alekseev, 1959: 90 - Tellerman Forest; Skufyin, 1978: 76 - southeast of the black-earth center (Voronezh Region with neighbor parts of Lipetsk and Belgorod regions; Khalidov, 1995: 140 - Tatarstan; Magdeev, 2003: 207 - Samara Region, Zhiguli; Isaev, 2004: 65 - Ulyanovsk Region; Isaev et al., 2004: 38 - Ulyanovsk Region; Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004: 53, part. - Chernigov Region, Central Dnieper region, Donetsk Region; Negrobov et al. 2005: 602 - Voronezh Region (Borisoglebsk District); Tsurikov, 2006: 190 - Lipetsk Region; 2009: 211 - Lipetsk Region; Shumik, 2012: 30 - Krasnyi Styag, Pochep District, Bryansk Region; Dyachenko, 2018: 49 - Kursk Region: Glushkovo and L'gov districts; Negrobov & Maslova, 2018: 273 - Voronezh Region (Borisoglebsk District); Prisyi, 2019: 432 - Belgorod Region (districts: Borisovka, Prokhorovka, Shebekino, Valuyki);

Cerambyx (s. str.) *cerdo acuminatus*, Gubin & Martynov, 2023: 160 - Donetsk Region, Svyatogorsk environs.

Type locality. Russia, Samara, Barboshina Polyana.

Description. Body big, similar to the biggest specimens of the other European and Caucasian populations; antennae moderately long, in males extending beyond elytral apex with 2 or 3 apical joints; female antennae significantly shorter than elytra; prothorax with extremely rough pronotal sculpture similar to prothorax of *C. c. acuminatus*; anterior prothorax constriction without three regular plications; elytra more or less converging posteriorly with distinct apical spines; body length in available males: 50-63 mm, body length in available female: 54 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new subspecies is close to *C. c. acuminatus* because of rough pronotal sculpture. But *C. c. acuminatus* usually has anterior pronotal constriction with three regular transverse plications absent in *C. c. nikolaevi*, as well as in *C. c. cerdo*. Antennae in *C. c. nikolaevi* distinctly shorter than in *C. c. cerdo* or in *C. c. acuminatus*.

Material. Holotype, male, Russia, Kuybyshev (now Samara), Frunze Polyana (now Barboshina Polyana), 24.5.1975. S. Kitanin leg. -

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author's collection; 3 paratypes; 1 male, Samara Region, Zhiguli, 1969, D. Natura leg. - author's collection; 1 male, Donetsk Region, Slavyansk District, Bogorodichnoe environs (near Svyatogorsk), 18.07.1972 - collection of Donetsk University, biological faculty; 1 female, Donetsk Region, Slavyansk District, Bogorodichnoe environs (near Svyatogorsk), 26.06.1971 - collection of Donetsk University, biological faculty.

Distribution. The subspecies is widely distributed all around central part of European Russia (according to Dyachenko, 2017 - whole European Russia) and Eastern Ukraine. Known localities are: Samara; Bakhteevka environs, Ulyanovsk Region; Staraya Andreevka environs, Penza Region; Orenburg Region (no exact locality); Tatarstan (no exact locality); Cheboksary; Tellerman Forest, Voronezh Region; Lipetsk Region (no exact locality); L'gov environs, Kursk Region; Glushkovo environs, Kursk Region; Krasnyi Styag, Bryansk Region; Prokhorovka environs, Belgorod Region.

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1-2 - *Cerambyx cerdo nikolaevi* **ssp. n.**: 1 - holotype, male, Russia, Kuybyshev (now Samara), Frunze Polyana (now Barboshina Polyana), 24.5.1975. S. Kitanin leg. (author's photo); 2 - paratype, female, Donetsk Region, Bogorodichnoe environs near Svyatogorsk, 26.06.1971 - photo by A. Gubin.

3-4 - *Cerambyx cerdo cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758 (author's photos): 3 - male, Ukraine, Kirovograd Region, Znamenka, 16-23.6.2017, L. Demidova leg.; 4 - female with same label.

5-6 *Cerambyx cerdo acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853 (author's photos): 5 - male, Armenia, Megri, 30.6.2003 M. Danilevsky leg.; 6 - female, Azerbaijan, Avrora (now Hirkan), 11.06.1979, M. Danilevsky leg.

Map 1. Locations of *Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo nikolaevi* ssp. n.

1 - Samara; 2 - Bakhteevka environs, Ulyanovsk Region; 3 - Staraya Andreevka environs, Penza Region; 4 - Orenburg Region (no exact locality); 5 - Tatarstan (no exact locality); 6 - Cheboksary; 7 - Tellerman Forest, Voronezh Region; 8 - Lipetsk Region (no exact locality); 9 - L'gov environs, Kursk Region; 10 - Glushkovo environs, Kursk Region; 11 - Krasnyi Styag, Bryansk Region; 12 - Prokhorovka environs, Belgorod Region; 13 - Borisovka environs, Belgorod Region; 14 - Shebekino environs, Belgorod Region; 15 - Valuyki environs, Belgorod Region; 16 - Svyatogorsk environs, Donetsk Region.

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**Second contribution to the *Litargus jakli* species group
(Coleoptera: Mycetophagidae) from the Oriental Region**

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Key words: Taxonomy, new species, Coleoptera, Mycetophagidae, *Litargus*, Oriental Region.

Abstract: The following new species belonging to the *Litargus jakli* species group from the Oriental Region are described, illustrated and compared with similar species: *Litargus (Litargosomus) philippinensis* **sp. nov.** (Philippines); *Litargus (Litargosomus) kalimantanus* **sp. nov.** (Indonesia: Kalimantan).

Introduction

The *Litargus jakli* group species have been described from the Oriental Region (Háva 2023) and include five species (Háva 2021, Junk 2022, Háva 2023). During the determination of some unidentified material deposited in the Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien, two new species from The Philippines and Indonesia: Kalimantan Island belonged to *Litargus jakli* species group, were discovered and described.

Material and methods

The material is deposited in the following collections:

JHAC - Jiří Háva, Private Entomological Laboratory & Collection, Únětice u Prahy, Prague-West, Czech Republic;

NHMW - Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien, Austria (M. Seidel).

The size of beetles or of their body parts can be useful in species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made:

total length (TL) - linear distance from anterior margin of head to apex of elytra.

elytral width (EW) - maximum linear transverse distance.

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Specimens of the presently described species are provided with red, printed label with text as follows: „HOLOTYPE [or PARATYPE] *name of species* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2024”.

Results

Genus *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 **Subgenus *Litargosomus* Motschulsky, 1858**

***Litargus jakli* species group**

***Litargus (Litargosomus) philippinensis* sp. nov.**

Figs. 1-3

Description. Male. Body measurements TL 1.9-2.0 mm, EW 1.0-1.1 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; brown on dorsal and ventral surfaces, covered with short, yellow recumbent setation.

Head brown, finely punctate; covered by yellowish, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, entirely brown with brown setation, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 2); palpomeres brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown, flatt, rugose, with large and dense punctures, covered with yellow recumbent setation; widest at base, gradually narrowed anteriorly and posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum broadly triangular, with short recumbent yellow setation.

Elytra brown without colour patterns, covered by yellow recumbent setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 to apex. Epipleuron brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Meta-meso ventrite brown, with yellow recumbent setation. Prosternal process broad.

Legs entirely light brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

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Abdominal visible ventrites brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation.

Male genitalia (Fig. 3).

Female. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species differs from other known species belonging to the species group by the form of the body, structure of the antennae and male genitalia; it is externally similar to *L. jaechi* Háva, 2023, but differs from it by the structure of the antennae and the brown body.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Philippines, Mindoro, E Puerto Galera, Sabang, xi.1992, Jäch leg., (NHMW). Paratypes: (1 ♂): Philipp., Negros Isl., Mambucal, 12.2.1994, Seyfert leg., (NHMW); (1 ♂): Philippines, Luzon, Lucena City, 23.11.1992 at light, Jäch leg., (JHAC).

Etymology. Toponymic, named after the Philippines.

Litargus (Litargosomus) kalimantanus sp. nov.

Figs. 4-5

Description. Female. Body measurements TL 1.9-2.0 mm, EW 1.0 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; brown on dorsal and ventral surfaces, covered with short, intermixed yellow and brown recumbent setation.

Head brown, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by yellowish, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, entirely light brown with yellow setation, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 5); palpi brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures, covered with intermixed yellow and brown recumbent setation; widest at base, gradually narrowed anteriorly and posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum broadly triangular, with short recumbent yellow setation.

Elytra brown without colour patterns, covered by intermixed yellow and brown recumbent setation, elongate, subparallel-sided.

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Epipleuron brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Metameso ventrite brown, with yellow recumbent setation. Prosternal process narrow.

Legs entirely brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdominal visible ventrites brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation.

Male. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species differs from other known species belonging to the species group by the form of body and structure of antennae; externally similar to *L. jakli* Háva, 2021, but differs from it by the structure of antennae, narrow prosternal process and intermixed brown and yellow setation on dorsal surfaces.

Type material. Holotype (♀): Indon., W Kalimantan, Nanga Ela env., 700 m, Nanga Nyuruh, 4-10.7.1993, Schneider leg., (NHMW). Paratype (1 ♀): same data as holotype, (JHAC).

Etymology. Toponymic, named after the Kalimantan Isl.

List of *Litargus jakli* species group

Litargus horaki Háva, 2023

Distribution: Thailand, Vietnam.

Litargus jaechi Háva, 2023.

Distribution: Thailand.

Litargus jakli Háva, 2021

Distribution: Indonesia, Timor.

Litargus jejuoensis Jung, 2022

Distribution: South Korea, Jeju.

Litargus jendeki Háva, 2023

Distribution: India, Meghalaya.

Litargus kalimantanus sp. nov.

Distribution: Indonesia, Kalimantan.

Litargus philippinensis sp. nov.

Distribution: The Philippines.

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Figs. 1-3. *Litargus (Litargosomus) philippinensis* sp. nov.: 1- body, dorsal aspect; 2- antennae; 3- male genitalia.

Figs. 4-5. *Litargus (Litargosomus) kalimantanus* sp. nov.: 4- body, dorsal aspect; 5- antennae.

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***Brachyta bifasciata* (Olivier, 1795) - protected name
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, homonym, ICZN.

Abstract: *Brachyta bifasciata* (Olivier, 1795) (not *Leptura bifasciata* O.F. Müller, 1776) is declared as a protected name because of prevailing usage according to the Art. 23.9. of ICZN (1999). More than 25 works, published by more than 10 authors in preceding 50 years are listed.

Common name *Brachyta bifasciata* (Olivier, 1795) originally introduced as *Leptura bifasciata* Olivier, 1795 is well known as a junior homonym (not *Leptura bifasciata* O.F. Müller, 1776) - Art. 53.3 - Danilevsky (2020: 155). The name must be protected according to the prevailing usage (Art. 23.9. of ICZN 1999). The junior homonym has been used for a particular taxon, as its presumed valid name, in at least 25 works, published by at least 10 authors in the immediately preceding 50 years and encompassing a span of not less than 10 years.

More than 25 works, published by more than 10 authors in preceding 50 years are:

Agafonova et al. (2022), Anisimov & Bezborodov (2020), Chiang & Chen (2001), Danilevsky (2010, 2014, 2020), Hayashi (1980), Hua (2002), Hwang (2015), Jang et al. (2015), Jałoszyński et al. (2014), Korsun et al. (2012), Lin & Yang (2019), Lobanov et al. (1981), Löbl & Smetana (2010), Ohbayashi (1984, 2007), Ohbayashi et al. (1992), Švácha (1989), Smirnov (2009), Tsherepanov (1979, 1988, 1990, 1996), Tshernyshev & Dubatolov (2005), Wang (2003, 2014), Wang et al. (2012), Xu & Neng (2010), Xu et al. (2007).

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